

DELIVERABLE D1.2 V2

SAMPLE ANALYSIS USING INDIVIDUAL OMIC TECHNIQUES AND DATA OUTPUTS

WP1 – Multi-omic technologies for Personalised Medicine

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The critical scientific output of the EATRIS-Plus project is to develop a Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX, D3.5¹, <https://motbx.eatris.eu/>) available for researchers to understand the molecular profiles in personalised medicine better. For the Multi-omics Toolbox, is vital to provide an example data set along with applied standard operational protocols (SOPs).

The main goal was to perform single omics analyses at the individual EATRIS sites across Europe on the same biological samples. Both the analytical and data processing steps were performed and are the basis for integrative multi-omics analyses (WP2, Tasks 2.1 and 2.2). Those integrative analysis workflows will be made available as part of the MOTBX and analysis results will be published in scientific articles.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Our flagship project EATRIS-Plus aims to build additional capabilities and deliver innovative scientific tools to support the long-term sustainability strategy of EATRIS as one of Europe's key European research infrastructures for Personalised Medicine.

The main goals of the EATRIS-Plus will be to:

- Consolidate EATRIS capacities in the field of Personalised Medicine (particularly omics technologies) to better serve academia and industry and augment the number of EATRIS Innovation Hubs with large pharma;
- Drive patient empowerment through active involvement in the infrastructure's operations;
- Expand strategic partnerships with research infrastructures and other relevant stakeholders, and
- Further, strengthen the long-term sustainability of the EATRIS financial model.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

The biological samples from the Czech cohort (n=127) were analysed by individual "omics" approaches (genomics, transcriptomics, epigenomics, proteomics, metabolomics) at different EATRIS sites across Europe (see Figure 1). Study subjects were informed and consented to provision of the data related to their person for research and development purposes to existing and future research partners of IMTM in an anonymous form (pseudonymized, from the definition of GDPR, while only IMTM holds the additional information)².

¹ The Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX): Empowering Multi-omics Research and Analysis for the Translational Medicine Community. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10141669>

² Further information available in the Ethics Deliverable 10.1 V1.1- Appendix 4

Figure 1: Overview of biological samples and omics measurements of the Czech multi-omics cohort.

The preparation of samples was performed according to the standard operation protocols collected and presented in D1.1. The generated data were analysed using protocols applied for the data analyses of single omics, as discussed during the meeting of WP2. Data were further evaluated, and statistical analyses were performed. Please see the section “Description of work” and subsequent subsections for the specific outputs.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

Here we are describing methods and outputs applied in individual “omics” technologies:

1) Genomics – metDNA Seq (UU)

Sequencing libraries were prepared from 100ng DNA using the NEBNext Enzymatic Methyl-seq sample preparation kit (cat# E7120S/E7120L, NEB) with unique dual indexes. The library preparation was performed according to the manufacturers’ instructions (manualE7120) including the addition of control DNAs (pUC19 and Lambda). Library quality check was performed using Fragment Analyzer and the DNF-910 dsDNA kit (Agilent). The libraries were quantified by qPCR using the Library quantification kit for Illumina (KAPA Biosystems) on a CFX384 Touch instrument (Bio-Rad) prior to pooling and sequencing. Sequencing was done on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 system to a minimum of 300 M paired-end reads for each sample (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Read length for the paired-end run was 2x151 bp.

Sequencing data was demultiplexed and converted from base calls into FASTQ files using Illumina bcl2fastq2 Conversion Software v2.20.0.422. Quality control after sequencing was performed using the in-house quality control tools CheckQC (<https://github.com/Molmed/checkQC>) and Seqreports (<https://github.com/Molmed/seqreports>) as well as FastQ Screen from Babraham Bioinformatics (https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastq_screen/). Primary methylation sequencing data analysis was performed with nf-core analysis pipeline methylseq version 1.6.1., the reference genome used was Ensembl GRCh38, release 105. Pipeline output include alignment to reference genome, methylation calls and various quality metrics.

Quality control after primary analysis consisted of PCA on the sites (overlapping (~3000) a set of array probes selected for sex classification (Wang, Y., Hannon, E., Grant, O.A. et al. DNA methylation-based sex classifier to predict sex and identify sex chromosome aneuploidy. *BMC Genomics* 22, 484 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-021-07675-2>).

The controls pUC19 and lambda were aligned using Bismark version 0.23.0 (Babraham Bioinformatics) and the methylation rate was compared against threshold provided by vendor.

For more details see D1.1.

To prepare the data for data analysis, we used the methrix v 1.10.0 R/Bioconductor package. We generated a methrix object using BSgenome.Hsapiens.NCBI.GRCh38 as a reference genome. Samples failed on prior QC measures for sequencing for low conversion rate ($n=2$) or low alignment rate ($n=3$) were excluded from further The resulting object was further filtered by removing all sites covered by less than 5 reads in more than 50% of the samples. All individual measurements were changed to missing if the coverage was less than 5 for a given sample. The sites not covered by any of the samples were removed from the dataset. The sites overlapping with common SNPs were removed using the remove_snps function as implemented in the methrix R package. SNPs with a minor allele frequency > 0.01 in any of the populations included in 1kGenomes based on MafDb.1Kgenomes.phase3.hs37d5 data package. Cell-type composition was assessed using an in-house implementation of the reference-based Houseman algorithm (<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-13-86>) using DNA methylation from the recently published DNA methylation atlas (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05580-6>).

For further analyses, we have prepared smaller, filtered datasets as follows:

1. 10000 randomly selected CpG sites among those covered in all patients
2. 10000 most variable CpG sites among those covered in all patients
3. 10000 randomly selected CpG sites, with the beta values adjusted for cell type composition
4. 10000 most variable CpG sites, with the beta values adjusted for cell type composition

2) Genomics - WGS (IMTM)

SAMPLE PREPARATION:

The TruSeq DNA PCR-Free LT Kit (Illumina) was used to prepare samples for whole genome sequencing. WGS libraries were prepared according to the manufacturer's protocol. The input DNA amount for WGS library preparation with genomic DNA for TruSeq-PCR-free libraries was 1 µg. The same fragmentation conditions for all samples on Covaris instrument were used with a targeted size of 350 bp.

The concentration of the TruSeq DNA PCR-Free libraries for WGS was measured by fluorometry using Qubit 2.0 fluorometer with HS dsDNA Assay kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, Q32854). The samples were equimolarly pooled based on the measured concentration and final quality check of sample pool was measured by qPCR with the KAPA Library Quantification Complete Kit (Universal) (Roche, KK4824); by fluorometry using Qubit 2.0 fluorometer with HS dsDNA Assay kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, Q32854);

and by capillary electrophoresis using 2100 Bioanalyzer instrument (Agilent) with the High Sensitivity DNA Kit (Agilent, 5067-4626).

For the WGS library preparation, the sequencing was performed using Illumina platform NovaSeq 6000 at 2×161 bases read length using the S4 configuration (cat# 20028312). Sequencing was performed following the manufacturer's instructions.

DATA PROCESSING:

Raw sequencing data were processed to obtain sequence. Briefly, the quality control (QC) was performed using the FastQC v0.11.9. The low-quality reads and adapter contamination trimming was performed by the fastp v0.20.1. The remaining reads were aligned to the reference human genome hg38/GRCh38 primary assembly by a software package BWA v0.7.17-r1188 with default parameters following by marking duplicate reads and fix mate information using Picard tools 2.27.5 (Picard Toolkit." 2018. Broad Institute, GitHub Repository. <http://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>; Broad Institute).

QC steps and the coverage were checked using the in-house software Genovesa (<https://www.bioxsys.eu/#/genovesa>) (developed by Bioxsys, s.r.o). Single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) and insertion/deletion variants (indels) were called using the VarScan v2.4.4 (VarScan: Variant detection in massively parallel sequencing of individual and pooled samples Koboldt D.C. Chen K. Wylie T. Larson D.E. McLellan M.D. Mardis E.R. Weinstock G.M. Wilson R.K. Ding L. Bioinformatics, 2009) (with parameters `--min-coverage 20; --min-var-freq 0.1; --p-value 0.5, --min-avg-qual 15`). The variant calling process is based on a Fisher's Exact test (applying algorithms Samtools, Varscan, Freebayes, and their combinations), a statistical test procedure that calculates an exact probability value for the relationship between two dichotomous variables, as found in two by two crosstable. The program calculates the difference between read counts supporting reference and variant alleles with a P-value threshold 0.05.

GATK pipeline best practice with default parameters (Dragen analogy) Data pre-processing for variant discovery (<https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us>)

Only SNVs and indels passing the quality filter (a minimal quality of coverage $\geq 30X$, base quality ≥ 10 , mapping quality ≥ 5) and with an alternative allele frequency $\geq 20\%$ per sample, P-value (Fisher exact test) 0.05 were included for further variant filtering.

CNVs were called using two different bioinformatics pipelines. The first approach was based on the depth calculation and normalization using the R software v3.6.0 (R Core Team (2020). R: A language and environment for statistical computing in covered exons (Packages: GenomInfoDb (4.0.3), GenomInfoDbData (4.0.3), GenomicAlignments (4.0.3), GenomicRanges (4.0.3), markdown (4.0.3), Matrix (4.0.3), MatrixGenerics (4.0.3), matrixStats (4.0.3), Rsamtools (4.0.3), rstudioapi (4.0.5), rversions (4.0.5), S4Vectors (4.0.3), sass (4.0.3)). Those exons which failed the mapability criteria (lower than 0.75 defined using 35-mer mapability score from UCSC genome browser) were excluded from the analysis. The read depth coverage base line was created using ≥ 6 samples and then the algorithm compared each sample to each. The ratio of expected reads to real number of reads was calculated to estimate a gain or loss in any specific locus defined by target.

3) Genomics - aCGH (IMTM)

Method is based on complementary binding of tested DNA to 2.6 million oligonucleotide markers immobilized on microarray cartridge. Obtained fluorescent intensities are statistically processed and sample genotype changes are obtained by comparing to reference model.

Array type: CytoScan HD (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

Total genomic DNA (130ng) was fragmented, labelled with fluorescent dyes and hybridized onto the microarray according the manufacturer instructions.

Arrays were scanned using GeneChip Gene Scanner 3000 7G (Thermo Fisher Scientific), the fluorescent intensity for each oligonucleotide markers were measured and .DAT files (image file) were generated.

Each marker has its own known position on the array, using annotation library the fluorescent intensity for each marker were calculated and .CEL files were subsequently generated.

The scanning process and generating of .DAT and .CEL files were performed using Affymetrix GeneChip Command console version.

Data analysis: .CEL files were annotated and analysed using Chromosome analysis suite (CHAS)(Applied Biosystems by Thermo Fisher Scientific), version 3.3.0.139 (r10838) and genome version hg38. The generated .CYCHP files were viewed using CHAS.

Table of Array Data Quality Control Metrics for all 126 processed CELL files (Filename column) corresponding to the Czech Cohort samples (ID column) was exported from CHAS. Results of the QC can be found in 'Threshold.Test' column: 'Within Bounds' states for samples which passed all three control:

- 1) MAPD (Median of the Absolute values of all Pairwise Differences) – a global measure of the variation of all microarray probes across the genome. It represents the median of the distribution of changes in Log2 Ratio between adjacent probes – it is a measure of short-range noise in the microarray data. Based on an empirical testing dataset, it has been determined that array data with MAPD > 0.25 has too much noise to provide reliable copy number calls.
- 2) SNPQC – a metric that estimates the distributions of homozygous AA, heterozygous AB and homozygous BB alleles and calculates the distance between them. When the SNPQC value is below 15, the noise within the array is higher than normal which compromises the overall data quality and clarity of results.
- 3) Waviness.SD – refers to an effect seen in genomic microarrays as a long-range variation. The long-range variation measurement is accomplished by calculating the variation in Log2 Ratios across the whole genome and subtracting out the short-range variation, specifically, for autosomal probes. A Waviness-SD value below 0.12 for CytoScan® arrays indicates that the long-range variation is within levels that can be accommodated by the CytoScan® algorithms.

For all 118 files which passed the QC w.log2ratio R Data object has been created. The data frame consisted of rows corresponding to the CN and SNP probes and columns: ProbeSetName (name of the probeset), Chromosome (chromosome number: 1-22, 24 for X, 25 for Y), Position (genomic position in the chromosome) and 118 columns with samples signal restored log2 ratio (WeightedLog2Ratio column from the probeset file) values. This file/object served as an input of segmentation process.

SEGMENTATION

Three algorithms implemented in ADaCGH2 Bioconductor package (Diaz-Uriarte, 2014) have been used – DNACopy (a parallelized wrapper for segmentation function from DNACopy Bioconductor package), HaarSeg (implementation of <https://github.com/HenrikBengtsson/HaarSeg>) and HMM (a parallelized wrapper for segmentation function from aCGH Bioconductor package), for segmentation based on the subset of CN probes (1.953.036 features) of w.log2ratio dataset.

For all variants of segmentation files common regions for all 118 samples were created but the row size of resulted matrix (the number of common regions) was in each case incredibly high: 1.157.589 (DNACopy), 1.629.670 (HaarSeg), 1.950.571 (HMM). Filtering segments according to the aberration threshold 0.3 lead to substantial but not sufficient decrease of feature numbers – 477.816 (DNACopy), 721.602 (HaarSeg), 532.520 (HMM), so the GISTIC software (Mermel C, Schumacher S, et al., 2011) which identifies regions of the genome that are significantly amplified or deleted across a set of samples (in our case the Czech Cohort – healthy blood donors) is planned to be used to make a reasonable sized multi-omics integration ready aCGH dataset.

REFERENCES

R Diaz-Uriarte. ADaCGH2: parallelized analysis of (big) CNA data. *Bioinformatics*, 30(12):1759--1761, 2014.

Mermel C, Schumacher S, et al. (2011). "GISTIC2.0 facilitates sensitive and confident localization of the targets of focal somatic copy-number alteration in human cancers." *Genome Biology*, 12:R41.

4) Transcriptomics – mRNAseq (FIMM)

Library preparation from 800 ng of total RNA was performed according to Illumina stranded mRNA prep Reference Guide (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Library quality check was performed using LabChip GX Touch HT High Sensitivity assay (PerkinElmer, USA). Normalized and pooled libraries were quantified using KAPA Library Quantification Kit (KAPA Biosystems, Wilmington, MA, USA) and sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 system to a minimum of 50 M paired-end reads for each sample (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Read length for the paired-end run was 2x151 bp.

Sequencing data is demultiplexed and converted from base call files into FASTQ files with Illumina bcl2fastq2 Conversion Software v.2.20. Sequencing was performed in multiple batches, each with a reference sample Brain RNA for normalization purposes (Human brain total RNA (Thermo Fisher AM7962))

Primary RNA-sequencing data analysis is performed with in-house Nextflow-based FIMM-RNAseq data analysis pipeline version 2.0.1. Pipeline outputs include alignments to reference genome and various quality metrics.

For more details see D1.1.

Principal component analysis:

Batches are indicated by colours. No significant effect of unwanted variation is evident.

Correlation heatmap:

Batches are indicated by colors. No significant effect of unwanted variation is evident.

Batch effect adjustment was performed using *ComBat* from R library *sva* (version 3.44.0). The parametric method using sex as covariate was applied. Principal Component Analysis was applied to visualize the differences before and after batch-effect adjustment:

5) Transcriptomics – MicroRNAseq (FIMM)

A clean up of the samples was performed using the miRNA micro kit from QIAGEN (cat. no. 74004). microRNA was eluted using 15 ul RNase-free water Library preparation from 600 ng of total RNA was performed in batches of 6-24 samples according to Lexogen Small RNA-Seq library prep Reference Guide (Lexogen GmbH, Vienna, Austria). Library quality check was performed using Agilent Bioanalyzer High Sensitivity DNA assay (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) and libraries were pooled based on the concentrations acquired from the assay. The pooled libraries were subjected to size selection targeting fragments that were 130-180 bp in size using BluePippin (Sage Science, Beverly, Massachusetts, USA). The size selected library pools were quantified using KAPA Library Quantification Kit (KAPA Biosystems, Wilmington, MA, USA) and sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq6000 system for 100 cycles using S1 flow cell with a lane divider to a minimum read depth of 10 M reads for each sample (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). Read length for the single-end run was 101 bp.

Sequencing data is demultiplexed and converted from base call files into FASTQ files with Illumina bcl2fastq2 Conversion Software v.2.20.

Primary miRNA-sequencing data analysis is performed with FIMM/UH-in-house Nextflow-based FIMM-smRNAseq data analysis pipeline. General output includes a sample-specific read count file describing the number of reads mapping to each miRNA and an alignment visualization file.

For more details see D1.1.

PCA plot for 1) Hairpin microRNAs and 2) Mature microRNAs.

1)

2)

Correlation heatmap for 1) Hairpin microRNAs and 2) Mature microRNAs

1)

2)

Batch effect adjustment was performed using *ComBat* from the R package *sva* (version 3.44.0). The parametric method using sex as covariate was applied. Batch 6 consists of only one single sample, through which it is not possible to include in the batch-correction. Principal Component Analysis was

applied to visualize the differences before and after batch-effect adjustment:

This plot shows that the un-corrected sample in batch 6 is a clear outlier in the batch-adjusted data. Hence, this sample should not be included for downstream analysis.

6) Transcriptomics – microRNAqRTPCR (SERMAS)

Total RNA enriched in miRNAs was isolated using miRNeasy Serum/plasma advanced kit (217204, QIAGEN) starting from 250ul of serum and eluted in a final volume of 25ul, following the manufactures instructions.

Before RNA isolation, 1ul of synthetic RNA Spike-in was added to each sample (miRCURY RNA Spike-in kit). Spike in further amplification serves as technical control of RNA extraction efficiency homogeneity.

We used the Universal RT miRNA PCR System (Qiagen) for cDNA synthesis. Briefly, 16ul of RNA was used as a template for RT in a final volume of 80 μ L. An external RNA (cel-miR-39) was added and further amplified to cDNA synthesis efficiency control.

Sample hemolysis was checked by miR-23a-3p and miR-451a amplification. Samples in which the subtraction of the expression of these miRNAs is higher than 7.5 were discarded due to elevated levels of hemolysis.

179 miRNA expression was evaluated by qRT-PCR using microRNA Array Profiling (miRCURY LNA miRNA Focus Panels; YAHS-106YG, Qiagen). All reactions were carried out in triplicate using a Light Cycler 480 instrument (Roche, Basel, Switzerland), and Cq values were calculated using a 2nd derivative method (Light Cycler 480 Software 1.5, Roche).

Data from miRNA-qPCR is stored in individual files that include two different replicates per file. QC process and analysis workflow were performed in R. Raw Cq values were transformed to Z-scores and normalized among plates, replicates and samples. Replicates with missing values higher than 18 miRNAs (~10% of the miRNAs) were removed from the analysis. Internal controls (mean of UniSP2 > 25, mean of cel_39 > 30 and N° of missing values > 40%) were used to remove samples from the study.

Batch effect was tested for extraction and RT. To test the effect of these steps, a PERMANOVA test (adonis2 function from vegan R package) was performed. Both extraction and RT were significantly associated to the data.

To remove the batch effect, Combat method (sva R packages) was used.

To test the effect of the batch effect removal, PERMANOVA test was performed again. Now, both RT and extraction are not associated with the data.

Clinical data association was tested with PERMANOVA test. RH Blood Group and Age were significantly associated with the miRNA profiles. Individual test was performed using robust statistical methods (WRS2 R package). Bootstrap Yuen's test for trimmed means was used for bivariate variables and Bootstrap version of the heteroscedastic one-way ANOVA for trimmed means for variables with more than 2 levels.

7) Proteomics (IMTM)

Plasma peptide mixtures were prepared from plasma samples by the FASP protocol adapted from Wisniewski JR. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2018;1841:3-10. The protein concentration was determined by BCA assay, and 100 µg of total proteins were processed. All processed plasma samples were diluted onto a 0,1 µg/µl concentration. Dilution was based on the results from the peptide concentration assay (for detailed information, see SOP_sample preparation for plasma analysis). During dilution, PROCAL peptides (JPT, cat. n. RTK-1-100pmol) are added to obtain a final concentration of 10 fmol/µl. Each sample was analyzed in two technical replicates. The 1 µg of peptides and 100 fmol of PROCAL peptides in injection volume 10 µl for 1 technical replicate were used. Peptides were separated by liquid chromatography (UltiMate 3000 RS series, Thermo Scientific™) and detected by mass

spectrometry (Orbitrap Fusion™ Tribrid™, Thermo Scientific™). Measurements of all 127 Czech Cohort samples consisted of 4 batches. Each batch started with an SST Test (5 injections of BSA standard); samples were released for analysis based on the results of the SST. The 10 injections of plasma peptide samples (5 samples in duplicate) and 1 BSA standard are running repeatedly until all plasma samples in the batch were measured. All detailed parameters of liquid chromatography and mass spectrometry settings are described in SOP_LC-MS_HCD_OT_Plasma analysis. Raw data of each technical replicate were searched in Proteome Discoverer software, ver. 2.5 (Thermo Scientific) in two subsequent steps -the processing and consensus steps. The processing workflow included a search against the complete human UniProtKB database, including Swiss-Prot reviewed and TrEMBL computationally analyzed but unreviewed proteins (<https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/>, downloaded in July 2020). In the consensus step, the normalization of abundances was done on specific protein amounts of PROCAL peptides. Detailed settings of both steps have been described in the SOP_Search_PD2.5_Plasma analysis. Results with identified and quantified proteins were exported from PD 2.5 in tab-separated format and processed with software R.

LOG2 TRANSFORMATION, AGGREGATION, FEATURE FILTERING AND MISSING VALUES IMPUTATION

The raw abundances were log2 transformed to make data distribution close to normal. Replicates abundances were aggregated by mean and three filters after exclusion of QC feature were applied:

1. 979 proteins completely missing at least in one batch were excluded,
2. 29 low FDR confidence proteins were removed.
3. only features with no more than 30 % of missing values were kept in the dataset.

After filtering the dataset consisted of 1393 proteins (features) abundances in rows and 127 samples (complete Czech Cohort) in columns with 7.9 % of missing values in total. A local similarity random forest method implemented in missForest R package (Stekhoven D. J., & Buehlmann, P., 2012) was chosen for imputation and a dataset with complete observation has been created.

BATCH ANALYSIS AND CORRECTION

Batch uncorrected dataset with missing values was used as an input of batch correcting process. Partial redundancy analysis (RDA), implemented in vegan R package (Oksanen J et al., 2022), estimated a proportion of constrained variability (Sex factor) as 5.3 % while a proportion of conditioned variability (Batch) as 37.6 %. This strong batch effect is also visible in graphical representation of batch uncorrected data in form of PCA plot (for PCA the dataset with imputed values was used) with confidence regions colored by batch.

Figure 1: PCA plot (first two components) for batch uncorrected dataset with imputed missing values; confidence regions colored by batch factor and Sex factor.

Three methods of batch correction – 1) the feature-level median method, implemented in proBatch R package (Cuclina, J., 2018), 2) the ComBat method and 3) the Combat method with Sex factor as a covariate, both implemented in sva R package, were used for batch correction. The best results were obtained for the last method – a proportion of constrained variability (Sex factor) 2.3 % and a proportion of conditioned variability (Batch) 0.3 %.

Figure 2: PCA plot (first two components) for ComBat with Sex as covariate batch corrected dataset with imputed missing values; confidence regions colored by batch factor and Sex factor.

It has been proved (Nygaard et al., 2016) that the batch correction methods that remove batch effects while retaining group differences may lead to deflated estimates of the estimation errors in consequent analysis in case of group-batch unbalanced design.

This behavior was observed in the univariate analysis provided by robust linear models of feature abundance with sex as an independent factor implemented in MASS R package (Venables, W. N., Ripley, B. D., 2002). The highest number (148 features) of significant results – 5 % level of significance, p-value calculated by method implemented in sfsmisc R package (Maechler M, 2023) and corrected by Benjamini-Hochberg method, was obtained for data corrected by ComBat method with Sex as a covariate.

Figure 3: Volcano plots of regression coefficient (x-axis) and corresponding adjusted p-values (y-axis) for results of univariate robust linear models of protein abundances for each of four explored datasets: batch uncorrected data (batch adjusted model), feature-level median batch corrected dataset, ComBat batch corrected dataset and ComBat with Sex as covariate batch corrected dataset.

In case of unbalanced batch design using of univariate models with adjustment to batch factor might be more appropriate than batch correction of the data. For this approach 29 proteins were revealed as significant and all of them was identified as significant features also for ComBat with Sex as a covariate batch corrected dataset. Only one protein was significant for each of all three batch corrected datasets and adjusted models for batch uncorrected data with no other significant features in case of feature-level median batch corrected dataset and ComBat batch corrected dataset.

It is not convenient to use batch uncorrected data for multi-omics integration and analyses. To choose the best batch corrected dataset the power of discrimination between male and female samples for each of the four datasets with usage of Support Vector Machines (SVM) models, implemented in e1071 R package (Meyer D et al., 2023), and LASSO models, implemented in glmnet R package (Friedman J et al., 2010), was explored.

Samples were divided into 5 folds and for each i -th fold, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, the separate models of sex and batch were fitted on the rest 4/5 of samples (training data), tested on the i -th fold samples (test data) and expressed as error rates. For both multivariate modelling methods – SVM and LASSO, the best behavior was observed for ComBat with Sex covariate batch corrected dataset. Models based on this dataset fitted sex well (SVM models, test error rates = 8 %, 21 %, 16 %, 0 %, 0 %; LASSO models, test error rates = 16 %, 13 %, 16 %, 7 %, 13 %) while batch with high error rates: SVM = 100 %, 100 %, 100 %, 100 %, 96 %, LASSO = 76 %, 71 %, 81 %, 59 %, 71 % which means that the dataset kept the Sex factor influence while the batch effect has been removed.

UNIVARIATE ANALYSIS

An influence of biological factors on protein abundances were studied by using robust linear models (rLM) of each protein abundance with a biological factor as an independent variable. ComBat with Sex as a covariate batch corrected dataset with missing values imputed by Random Forest method was used. To correct an overconfidence in the results, the significant features (5 % level of significance, p-values corrected for multiple testing by Benjamini-Hochberg method) were compared also with results of batch adjusted robust linear models built for batch uncorrected dataset. The results of rLM analysis can be treated also like an ordered list of candidates, with the most likely true positives on top (Nygaard et al., 2016).

8) Targeted Metabolomics (RUMC)

DATA ACQUISITION

Quantitative targeted metabolomics data were acquired at Radboud university medical center (Radboudumc) and Maastricht UMC+ (MUMC+). Plasma acylcarnitine analysis (ACRN, 44 metabolites) was performed at Radboudumc according to a protocol previously described (Vreken, et al. 1999). Plasma amino acid analysis (AA, 53 metabolites) and very long chain fatty acid analysis (VLCFA, 5 metabolites) were performed at MUMC+ according a previously described (Waternal, et al. 2009) and an in-house protocol, respectively. Metabolite levels were reported as μM concentrations.

The 127 plasma samples from the Czech cohort were measured in multiple batches: four batches for ACRN, two batches for AA, and six batches for VLCFA analysis. For ACRN analysis, a mixture of compounds with known concentrations (quality control / QC sample) was measured along with each batch. For AA analysis, two different mixtures of compounds with known concentrations were measured along with each batch. For ACRN analysis, the limit of detection (LOD) is 0.01 μM . For AA analysis, the limits of quantification (LOQ) are below 1 μM , except for ethanolamine (hmdb:HMDB0000149) where LOQ is ~ 2.5 μM , and for formiminoglutamic acid (hmdb:HMDB0000854), 3-methylhistidine (hmdb:HMDB0000479), 1-piperidine-6-carboxylic acid (chebi:49015), and allysine (chebi:17027) for which LOQ were not determined. Metabolites that could not be detected (true value < LOD) were reported with a concentration of 0 μM . These values were imputed during data pre-processing (see section Missing value imputation).

DATA FAIRIFICATION

Raw spectral data are available in both vendor and open (mzML) format. Conversion of raw spectral data (.raw) to mzML format was performed with msconvert using the ProteoWizard and Skyline Docker image (<https://hub.docker.com/r/chambm/pwiz-skyline-i-agree-to-the-vendor-licenses>) (Chambers, et al. 2012).

The experimental metadata was captured using the Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) metadata framework (Sansone, et al. 2012) as is required for submission to EMBL EBI's MetaboLights archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>). The tabular ISA-Tab Investigation file describes the used assays, protocols, and ontologies. The ISA-Tab Study file describes the samples. The ISA-Tab Assay files describe the measurement process (sample preparation, chromatography, mass spectrometry) per cohort and QC sample referencing the protocols, specifying protocol parameters, raw and derived spectral files and Metabolite Assignment Files (MAF). The Assay files also contain information about

relevant technical factors (measurement date, number of freeze-thaw cycles). The ISA-JSON file contains all the above information in JSON format.

Measured compounds were annotated using the Metabolite Assignment File (MAF) format which also reports internal standards used for quantification and metabolite concentrations per sample. Each compound was annotated with a unique database identifier in the Compact Uniform Resource Identifier (CURIE) format.

INITIAL DATA ANALYSIS

Heatmaps showing the proportion of missing values per feature and batch were created. Metabolite concentrations were visualized using box plots.

REFERENCE VALUES

For reporting of reference values, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum μM metabolite concentrations were calculated across all individuals in the cohort. Additionally, corresponding values were determined for only male and only female individuals. One individual with Klinefelter syndrome was excluded from calculation of reference values.

IDENTIFICATION OF BATCH EFFECT

The presence of batch effects was assessed visually with principal component analysis (PCA) and sample correlation plots, and statistically using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and redundancy analysis (RDA).

Sample correlations were calculated in order to detect the presence of potential batch effects. Pearson correlation coefficient were calculated using complete pairwise observations.

Batch effects were detected using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) by comparing single metabolite levels of the different batch groups. This was performed for each metabolite measured by the different assays (ACRN, AA and VLCFA).

The multivariate constrained ordination method Redundancy Analysis (RDA) was performed to determine if variation in the metabolite levels (response variables) can be explained by the measurement date (batch, explanatory variable). Additionally, RDA was performed with sex as a conditional variable to determine if any effect of batch is still present when taking sex into account. For amino acids, it was additionally tested if differences in metabolite levels can be explained by the number of times samples were frozen and thawed. This was done with and without batch as conditional variable. Analyses were conducted using the R package *vegan* (Oksanen, et al. 2022).

DATA PRE-PROCESSING AND PREPARATION

FEATURE FILTERING

Metabolites missing in $\geq 30\%$ of the samples were removed.

LOG-TRANSFORMATION

Since metabolite concentrations follow a log-normal distribution more closely than a normal distribution, concentrations were log-transformed using the natural logarithm after adding a constant value to each value ($\log(x+1)$).

BATCH EFFECT ADJUSTMENT

Batch effect adjustment was performed using *ComBat* from the R/Bioconductor library *sva* (version 3.44.0). Both the parametric and the non-parametric method were applied. Both methods were applied using sex as covariate to retain information related to sex in an unbalanced batch design and without covariate.

MISSING VALUE IMPUTATION

While some analysis methods can handle missing values other methods require complete observations. Therefore, missing values were imputed. Since the metabolomics assays are quantitative targeted measurements, the true values are assumed to be between 0 μM and the lower limit of detection. This means that values are missing not at random (MNAR). Several imputation methods were applied including both methods recommended for values missing at random (MAR) and MNAR. The distributions of imputed values were visually compared to choose a suitable method. Criteria were that imputed values should be in the lower range of the observed values but not distorting the overall value distribution.

Random Forest

Missing value imputation with Random Forest was performed using the R package *missForest* (Stekhoven and Buhlmann 2012, Stekhoven 2022). Previously, this method was reported to be suitable for data with values MAR or missing completely at random (MCAR) (Wei, et al. 2018). The number of trees per forest was set to $n_{\text{tree}}=1000$ and the maximum number of iterations was set to $\text{maxiter}=10$. Out-of-bag (OOB) mean squared errors (MSE) were returned per variable (metabolite). Normalised root MSR (NRMSE) were calculated per variable as $\text{NRMSE}=\text{MSE}_{\text{mean}}(\text{observed})$.

k-nearest neighbours (kNN)

The R/Bioconductor package *impute* (Hastie, et al. 2022) was used to impute missing values using *k*-nearest neighbours averaging.

Quantile regression imputation of left-censored data (QRILC)

QRILC is implemented in the R package *imputeLCMD* (Lazar and Burger 2022). This method was previously described to be applicable for values that are MNAR (Wei, et al. 2018). To avoid distortion of the value distribution values are randomly drawn from a truncated normal distribution (Wei, et al. 2018).

No-skip kNN

No-skip kNN is a modified version of kNN developed for MNAR (Lee and Styczynski 2018). The internal function *nsKNN* from the R package *MAI* (Dekermanjian, Shaddox, et al. 2022a) was used to impute missing values.

Single imputation

This method is an alternative method for imputing values MNAR (Dekermanjian, Shaddox, et al. 2022). The internal function `kapImpute2` from the R package MAI (Dekermanjian, Shaddox, et al. 2022a) was employed.

Low abundance resampling (LAR)

Missing values were imputed by randomly sampling from the 5% observed values with lowest abundance.

Mechanism-aware imputation (MAI)

This two-step approach implemented in the R package MAI (Dekermanjian, Shaddox, et al. 2022a) first estimates the pattern of missingness (MNAR, MCAR) for each variable (Dekermanjian, Shaddox, et al. 2022). Based on the estimated missingness pattern, Random Forest is used for MCAR and no-skip-kNN is used for MNAR.

FEATURE STANDARDISATION

For downstream analyses, the metabolite features were mean-centred to zero and scaled to unit-variance.

RESULTS

MISSING VALUES AND FEATURE FILTERING

Metabolite levels (μM concentrations) were determined for all 127 plasma samples from the Czech cohort. Some metabolite levels were below the limit of detection. An overview of missing values in the different assays is given in Figure 1. The numbers of measured metabolites per assay before and after filtering features with $\geq 30\%$ missing values are given in Table 1.

Figure 1: Proportion of missing values per metabolite and measured batch as well as across all batches (total) for targeted metabolomics assays acylcarnitines, amino acids and very long chain fatty acids.

Table 1: Overview of numbers of measured metabolites before and after filtering based on proportion of missing values.

Assay	Number of analysed compounds	Number of compounds not detected in any sample	Number of compounds with ≥30% (and <100%) missing values	Number of compounds after filtering
ACRN	43	6	4	33
AA	53	0	7	46
VLCFA	5	0	0	5

Discussion points:

- Since the quantitative targeted metabolomics assays were developed to diagnose inborn errors of metabolism, it is possible that some of the analysed metabolites are not expected to be detectable in healthy individuals. This might explain why some compounds have a very high number of missing values.
- In the AA assay, some metabolites (glycylproline, carnosine, anserine) are almost only measured in one of the two batches. This might be (partially) caused by the unbalanced batch design (see Table 2) and biological differences between males and females, and/or by (unknown) technical factors. The metabolites were removed by filtering based on the overall proportion of missing values.

Table 2: Number of samples from males and females per batch and assay.

Assay	Batch	Number (percentage) of samples from female individuals	Number (percentage) of samples from male individuals
ACRN	2022-01-06	3 (13%)	20 (87%)
	2022-02-02	4 (15%)	22 (85%)
	2022-02-07	23 (64%)	13 (36%)
AA	2022-02-09	34 (81%)	8 (19%)
	2022-02-16	19 (27%)	52 (73%)
	2022-02-22	45 (80%)	11 (20%)
VLCFA	2022-02-18	10 (19%)	44 (81%)
	2022-02-25	5 (45%)	6 (55%)
	2022-03-04	11 (69%)	5 (31%)
	2022-03-10	18 (69%)	8 (31%)
	2022-03-11	20 (100%)	0 (0%)

MEASURED METABOLITE CONCENTRATIONS

Measured metabolite concentrations for the ACRN, AA and VLCFA assays (filtered features only, not transformed, not batch-adjusted) are summarized in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively.

Figure 2: Box plots of metabolite concentrations [µM] in males and females measured by plasma acylcarnitine analysis.

Figure 3: Box plots of metabolite concentrations [μM] in males and females measured by plasma amino acid analysis.

Figure 4: Box plots of metabolite concentrations [μM] in males and females measured by plasma very long chain fatty acid analysis.

DETECTION OF BATCH EFFECT

PCA score plots (Figure 5) indicate a slight batch effect especially for the AA assay. The plots also indicate that differences can at least partially be attributed to the unbalanced batch design (see also Table 2).

Figure 5: Principal Component Analysis score plots of targeted metabolomics assays (acylcarnitines, ACRN; amino acids, AA; very long chain fatty acids, VLCFA) before batch effect adjustment. Features with missing values were excluded from the analysis. Metabolite levels were log-transformed and standardised. Samples are colored by measurement date (left) and sex (right).

Sample correlations were visualized with heatmaps (Figure 6). Especially for the amino acids and acylcarnitines, these heatmaps indicate the presence of certain sample groups, which could correspond to the different measurement days.

Figure 6: Sample correlations matrices of the different targeted metabolomics assays.

Batch effects in the data were observed by performing ANOVA tests per metabolomics feature, comparing the groups of samples with different measurement dates. This showed that 21 out of 33 acylcarnitines were found to be significantly different in the different batches, where this was the case for 19 out of 46 amino acids (see Appendix). None of the very long chain fatty acids were found to be significantly different among the batches.

RDA was performed to determine if the measurement date (batch) can explain variation in the metabolite levels. To test if any observed variation explained by batch is still present when accounting for the unbalanced batch design (see Table 2), sex was included as a conditional variable in the RDA models. A summary of RDA results is shown in Table 4. Result visualisations are available in the Appendix. Variation in the metabolite levels that can be explained by batch is low (<9%) but the RDA model is significant for ACRN and AA. The variation explained by batch is lower when using sex as conditional variable but remains significant. For VLCFA, the effect of batch is only significant when accounting for sex. For ACRN, the effect of the number of times that samples were frozen/thawed is significant but not significant when accounting for batch.

Table 4: Summary of RDA results. Significance levels: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Formula	Proportion of variation explained by constrained axes	p-value	Significance level
ACRN ~ Measurement.date	0.071	0.0005	***
ACRN ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)	0.041	0.0342	*
ACRN ~ Number.of.freeze-thaw.cycles	0.025	0.0132	*
ACRN ~ Number.of.freeze-thaw.cycles + Condition(Measurement.date)	0.007	0.3797	
AA ~ Measurement.date	0.081	0.0001	***
AA ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)	0.028	0.0005	***
VLCFA ~ Measurement.date	0.038	0.2736	
VLCFA ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)	0.073	0.0113	*

BATCH EFFECT ADJUSTMENT

Based on the RDA results, it was decided to perform batch effect adjustment but include sex as a covariate to account for the unbalanced batch design. To choose between the parametric and non-parametric ComBat methods, prior probability distribution plots were assessed. The parametric method was deemed suitable as empirical kernel density estimates of batch effects and parametric estimates of batch effects overlap.

Discussion point:

- Due to the measured precision, the concentration distributions of some metabolites are discrete rather than continuous. In this case, ComBat produces values not observed in original unadjusted data.

MISSING VALUE IMPUTATION

Bee swarm plots (Figure 7, Figure 8) show that both Random Forest (OOB NRMSE ranged between 0.07 for citrulline and 0.91 for argininosuccinic acid) and MAI produced imputed values that range around the mean of the measured values. kNN produced imputed values higher than any measured values for some metabolites (5-aminolevulinic acid, saccharopine). QRILC clearly distorts the value distribution by producing extremely low values. No-skip kNN produced a mixture of values ranging around the mean of the measured values and low values. Both single imputation and LAR produced low values but the values imputed by LAR have a higher spread especially for beta-alanine and ethanolamine.

Figure 7: Distribution of measured and imputed metabolite levels. Prior to missing value imputation, metabolites were filtered, levels were log-transformed and batch effect-adjusted using the parametric ComBat method with sex as covariate. Imputation methods: RF, Random Forest; kNN, k-nearest neighbour; QRLIC, quantile regression imputation for left-censored data; NS-kNN, no-skip-kNN, Single, single imputation, LAR, low abundance resampling (5%), MAI, mechanism-aware imputation.

Figure 8: Distribution of measured and imputed metabolite levels (same data as Figure 5 but QRLIC was omitted). Prior to missing value imputation, metabolites were filtered, levels were log-transformed and batch effect-adjusted using the parametric ComBat method with sex as covariate.

Imputation methods: RF, Random Forest; kNN, k-nearest neighbour; NS-kNN, no-skip-kNN, Single, single imputation, LAR, low abundance resampling (5%), MAI, mechanism-aware imputation.

Based on our assumption that the pattern of missingness is MNAR and imputed values being low but not too similar to each other (which can distort the overall value distribution) we chose LAR for the subsequent analyses.

Downstream analysis

To determine which biological factors, contribute to the primary variation in the metabolomics data, PCA was performed on pre-processed (filtered, log-transformed, batch effect-adjusted, imputed, standardised) data and correlations of principal components (PCs) with phenotype and clinical haematology variables were determined. For ACRN, PC 2 explaining 9% of the variation in the data and PC 6 (4%) are significantly associated with sex. PC 2 is also correlated with height, which is confounded by sex. For AA, PC 1 (24%) is significantly associated with sex, height, weight, BMI, erythrocytes, haemoglobin, and haematocrit; PC 2 (8%) with mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC); PC 3 (6%) with sex, weight and leukocytes; and PC 5 (5%) with sex, weight, erythrocytes, haemoglobin, and haematocrit. For VLCFA, no associations were significant after correction for multiple testing. Observed differences between age groups, BMI groups or smoking behaviour groups were not significant correction for multiple testing in any of the assays.

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9) Untargeted Lipidomics (IMTM)

SAMPLE PREPARATION (HUMAN PLASMA):

Before the analysis, 50 µL of plasma (thawed on ice) was mixed with 150 µL of ice-cold LCMS isopropanol containing Avanti SPLASH internal standard mixture, FA 20:4(d8), Cer d18:1(d7)/15:0 and vortexed for 20 s. Samples were centrifuged (22400g, 20 mins @ 4°C), and 150 µL of the supernatant was loaded into a low recovery volume HPLC vial with insert. Blank samples were prepared using the same procedure instead of gradient fraction LCMS water. Pooled quality control samples (QC) were prepared by mixing 10 µL of plasma from every sample and thoroughly vortexed (5 min). Each QC (n=18) sample was prepared individually in the same way as the biological samples. QC sample was injected as every 6th sample through the analytical batch. The standard reference material samples (SRM NIST 1950) were prepared the same way as other biological samples and injected at the beginning and end of the analytical batch. Samples were randomised for the first time before the sample preparation. Second, separate randomisation was done for the data acquisition.

LCMS ANALYSIS:

Separation of non-polar compounds was done using reversed-phase chromatography separation mechanisms on an Accucore C30 column (150 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.6 µm; Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA). The constitution of mobile phase A was 20 mM ammonium formate in 60:40 (v:v) acetonitrile:water and mobile phase B consisted of 20 mM ammonium formate in 85.5:9.5:5 isopropanol:acetonitrile:water (v:v:v). The gradient was as follows: t= 0.0, 20% B; t= 2.5, 20% B, t= 2.6, 55% B; t= 12, 60% B; t= 12.1, 80% B; t= 19.0, 90% B; t= 21.0, 100% B; t= 23.0, 100% B; t= 23.1, 20% B; t= 30.0, 20% B. All changes were linear (curve = 5), and the flow rate was 0.400 mL.min⁻¹. The column temperature was 55 °C, and the injection volume was 2µL. Data were acquired separately in positive

OUTPUTS

Table 1 summarises the number of detected compounds in the dataset according to their identification confidence level.³ MSI ID Level 2 was done by comparing MSMS data to spectral database, followed by the assigning LipidMAPS ID (LMID) – this dataset will be used for following multi-omic analyses.

Table 1: Summary of detected and putatively annotated compounds by Compound Discoverer 3.3. SP1

	Positive	Negative
All compounds	3498	659
Annotations -10/+10 ppm	2331	440
MSI ID Level 3	960	243
MSI ID Level 2 (LMID)	196	175
MS/MS	1046	350

We have performed principal component analysis (PCA) to evaluate the human plasma samples (n=127) data in positive ionisation mode (Figure 2) and negative ionisation mode (Figure 3). Only putatively annotated compounds (positive ionisation mode, n=196; negative ionisation mode, n=175) were used to create PCA models. Main differences were observed based on gender segregation. The tight clustering of quality control samples in the middle of the PCA confirms a very low analytical variance in the data, leaving the rest of the clustering to biological influence.

Figure 2: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) showing 127 analysed plasma samples for positive ionisation mode based on 196 putatively annotated compounds (MSI ID Level 2). (Female samples – blue; Male samples – orange; NIST SRM 1950 – turquoise; Quality Control samples – pale green)

Figure 3: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) showing 127 analysed plasma samples for negative ionisation mode based on 175 putatively annotated compounds (MSI ID Level 2). (Female samples – blue; Male samples – orange; NIST SRM 1950 – turquoise; Quality Control samples – pale green)

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NEXT STEPS

The generated datasets will be used in Work Package 3 – Multiomics toolbox (MOTBX) - as example datasets. Simultaneously, the single omics data sets are ready for the multi-omic data integration.

ABBREVIATIONS

AA – amino acids; ACRN – acylcarnitines; ANOVA – analysis of variance; kNN – k-nearest neighbours; LAR – low abundance resampling; MAF – Metabolite Assignment File; MAI – mechanism-aware imputation; MAR – missing at random; MCAR – missing completely at random; MNAR – missing not at random; MSE – mean squared error; OOB – out-of-bag; PCA – principal component analysis; RDA – redundancy analysis; VLCFA – very long chain fatty acids; LCMS – liquid chromatography mass spectrometry; QC – quality control; SRM NIST – Standard reference material NIST; FWHM – full width at the half maximum; NCE – normalised collision energies; SERRF - Systematical Error Removal using Random Forest; RSD – relative standard deviation; MAD – median absolute deviation; MSI – Metabolomics Standards Initiative; LMID - LipidMAPS ID; PCA – principal component analysis

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

Deliverable is submitted by the expected due date 30/06/2023; adjusted deliverable submitted 08/12/2023.

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

As a recommendation of the EATRIS-Plus Ethics Committee, the Executive Summary portion was updated to better reflect results and conclusions. In addition, footnotes were added to Multi-omics Toolbox, as well as describing the consent and data sharing procedure of the Czech Cohort. In addition, and independent of the Ethics Committee review some figures were replaced with ones not containing individual sample labels.

APPENDICES

1. Targeted Metabolomics RUMC - Reference values

File	Targeted metabolomics Appendix/Reference values targeted metabolomics RUMC.pdf
Description	Reference values of targeted metabolomics measurements. Median, standard deviation (SD), minimum, and maximum values of metabolite concentration [μ M] for males, females and complete cohort.

2. Targeted Metabolomics RUMC - PCA and RDA visualisations

File	Targeted metabolomics Appendix/ PCAandRDA_ACRN_AA_VLCFA.pdf
Description	PCA sample score plots of filtered, log-transformed and standardized metabolite levels (for ACRN, AA, and VLCFA). Features with missing values were excluded.

RDA explained variation bar plots and sample score plots per RDA model.

3. Targeted Metabolomics RUMC - ANOVA significant hits

File	Targeted metabolomics Appendix/ Batch_effect_ANOVA.pdf
Description	Tables for both ACRN and AA assays, showing the metabolomics features that were found to be significantly different among the batches.

Reference values: metabolite concentrations [μM]			Male					Female					All				
Assay	Metabolite name	Database identifier (CURIE)	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N
AA	(2S)-2-[[[(2R)-2-amino-3-sulfanylpropanoyl]amino]-4-sulfanylbutanoic acid	pubchem.compound:54026778	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	40	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	17	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	57
AA	1-Methylhistidine	hmdb:HMDB0000001	3.72	8.09	0.32	40.76	62	2.09	8.58	0.40	58.77	64	2.70	8.33	0.32	58.77	126
AA	1-piperidine-6-carboxylic acid	chebi:49015	0.28	0.27	0.07	1.53	62	0.26	0.16	0.06	0.67	63	0.28	0.23	0.06	1.53	125
AA	3-Aminoisobutanoic acid	hmdb:HMDB0003911	1.40	0.57	0.68	3.23	62	1.15	0.58	0.52	3.45	64	1.24	0.58	0.52	3.45	126
AA	3-Methylhistidine	hmdb:HMDB0000479	4.73	1.42	3.19	10.46	62	3.63	1.27	1.94	9.53	64	4.00	1.45	1.94	10.46	126
AA	4-Hydroxyproline	hmdb:HMDB0000725	13.75	5.89	5.97	38.18	62	10.11	6.58	4.99	37.81	64	11.30	6.41	4.99	38.18	126
AA	5-Aminolevulinic acid	hmdb:HMDB0001149	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.13	50	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.13	41	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.13	91
AA	5-Hydroxylysine	hmdb:HMDB0000450	0.28	0.10	0.12	0.77	62	0.23	0.10	0.12	0.62	64	0.26	0.10	0.12	0.77	126
AA	Allocystathionine	hmdb:HMDB0000455	0.17	0.51	0.08	4.13	62	0.15	0.11	0.05	0.65	64	0.16	0.37	0.05	4.13	126
AA	allysine	chebi:17027	0.08	0.07	0.01	0.35	60	0.05	0.05	0.01	0.20	62	0.06	0.07	0.01	0.35	122
AA	Amino adipic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000510	1.75	0.50	0.90	3.06	62	1.23	0.65	0.60	4.85	64	1.47	0.62	0.60	4.85	126
AA	Anserine	hmdb:HMDB0000194	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.10	12	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	17	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.10	29
AA	Argininosuccinic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000052	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.34	61	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.34	56	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.34	117
AA	Aspartylglycosamine	hmdb:HMDB0000489	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.15	61	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.10	64	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.15	125
AA	beta-Alanine	hmdb:HMDB0000056	1.58	0.66	0.92	3.81	62	1.69	1.20	0.32	9.16	56	1.61	0.95	0.32	9.16	118
AA	Carnosine	hmdb:HMDB0000033	0.06	0.09	0.01	0.28	14	0.07	0.09	0.01	0.50	45	0.07	0.09	0.01	0.50	59
AA	Citrulline	hmdb:HMDB0000904	30.91	7.90	15.96	50.77	62	25.58	7.38	14.77	45.29	61	28.51	7.97	14.77	50.77	123
AA	Cysteine-S-sulfate	hmdb:HMDB0000731	0.18	0.09	0.04	0.26	4	0.01	NA	0.01	0.01	1	0.15	0.11	0.01	0.26	5
AA	Ethanolamine	hmdb:HMDB0000149	10.66	5.45	2.72	25.85	61	18.41	7.43	1.78	33.45	57	12.80	6.98	1.78	33.45	118
AA	Formiminoglutamic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000854	0.08	0.05	0.02	0.33	62	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.36	64	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.36	126
AA	gamma-Aminobutyric acid	hmdb:HMDB0000112	0.14	0.07	0.10	0.61	62	0.15	0.03	0.08	0.24	64	0.15	0.06	0.08	0.61	126
AA	Glycine	hmdb:HMDB0000123	210.44	43.14	150.43	355.56	62	226.11	94.33	114.52	587.17	64	218.05	75.01	114.52	587.17	126
AA	Glycylproline	hmdb:HMDB0000721	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.42	51	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	19	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.42	70
AA	Homocarnosine	hmdb:HMDB0000745	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	49	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	17	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	66
AA	Homocitrulline	hmdb:HMDB0000679	0.27	0.12	0.14	0.69	62	0.29	0.22	0.12	1.09	64	0.28	0.18	0.12	1.09	126
AA	L-Alanine	hmdb:HMDB0000161	445.06	85.93	188.01	665.95	62	391.25	97.00	218.42	676.84	64	421.77	93.38	188.01	676.84	126
AA	L-Alloisoleucine	hmdb:HMDB0000557	2.19	0.64	1.05	4.69	62	1.38	0.41	0.75	2.46	64	1.74	0.64	0.75	4.69	126
AA	L-alpha-Aminobutyric acid	hmdb:HMDB0000452	18.53	5.47	10.75	33.13	62	17.57	5.57	7.64	30.95	64	18.06	5.54	7.64	33.13	126
AA	L-Arginine	hmdb:HMDB0000517	64.40	22.89	20.92	144.76	62	65.72	18.47	25.20	101.47	64	64.71	20.69	20.92	144.76	126
AA	L-Asparagine	hmdb:HMDB0000168	44.51	8.50	23.82	65.08	62	46.03	8.42	25.40	66.36	64	45.44	8.43	23.82	66.36	126
AA	L-Aspartic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000191	6.78	2.91	3.12	16.41	62	5.01	2.02	2.32	14.92	64	5.69	2.68	2.32	16.41	126
AA	L-Cystine	hmdb:HMDB0000192	1.89	1.41	0.45	7.19	62	1.60	1.01	0.31	5.60	64	1.67	1.24	0.31	7.19	126
AA	L-Glutamic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000148	95.33	58.95	41.92	299.38	62	53.05	38.35	24.06	221.20	64	77.28	54.93	24.06	299.38	126
AA	L-Glutamine	hmdb:HMDB0000641	557.88	113.85	276.45	864.51	62	510.52	90.47	211.22	684.97	64	525.04	103.40	211.22	864.51	126
AA	L-Histidine	hmdb:HMDB0000177	89.92	11.14	70.17	119.49	62	82.42	11.14	59.04	110.62	64	86.51	11.65	59.04	119.49	126

Reference values: metabolite concentrations [μM]			Male					Female					All				
Assay	Metabolite name	Database identifier (CURIE)	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N
AA	L-Homocystine	hmdb:HMDB0000676	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.31	16	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	9	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.31	25
AA	L-Isoleucine	hmdb:HMDB0000172	72.65	14.43	41.84	135.49	62	52.39	15.31	27.91	116.15	64	63.13	17.60	27.91	135.49	126
AA	L-Leucine	hmdb:HMDB0000687	145.32	27.16	81.74	268.60	62	105.39	27.40	57.64	218.52	64	125.73	32.42	57.64	268.60	126
AA	L-Lysine	hmdb:HMDB0000182	197.26	34.93	125.25	305.49	62	181.36	37.89	105.50	286.16	64	186.24	37.57	105.50	305.49	126
AA	L-Methionine	hmdb:HMDB0000696	25.60	5.19	17.60	42.65	62	22.74	5.03	13.28	36.58	64	24.25	5.40	13.28	42.65	126
AA	L-Phenylalanine	hmdb:HMDB0000159	68.54	13.43	43.77	104.22	62	60.66	9.46	38.97	91.34	64	62.17	12.40	38.97	104.22	126
AA	L-Pipecolic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000716	2.00	1.10	0.85	6.78	62	1.63	1.01	0.66	5.33	64	1.78	1.06	0.66	6.78	126
AA	L-Proline	hmdb:HMDB0000162	234.78	53.73	109.03	361.50	62	176.06	52.20	86.72	314.96	64	198.27	58.96	86.72	361.50	126
AA	L-Serine	hmdb:HMDB0000187	100.47	16.41	53.00	136.44	62	105.62	21.54	61.42	147.97	64	101.97	19.19	53.00	147.97	126
AA	L-Threonine	hmdb:HMDB0000167	124.97	27.14	83.89	247.27	62	120.26	29.36	59.83	187.50	64	122.01	28.54	59.83	247.27	126
AA	L-Tryptophan	hmdb:HMDB0000929	74.61	11.83	51.00	101.00	62	65.90	10.98	41.56	105.71	64	68.62	12.06	41.56	105.71	126
AA	L-Tyrosine	hmdb:HMDB0000158	73.11	14.41	48.61	114.82	62	62.73	17.55	33.67	149.81	64	68.70	16.71	33.67	149.81	126
AA	L-Valine	hmdb:HMDB0000883	244.56	36.83	155.55	381.01	62	191.68	40.79	116.63	339.25	64	219.18	45.05	116.63	381.01	126
AA	O-Phosphoethanolamine	hmdb:HMDB0000224	3.24	0.58	1.93	4.70	62	2.51	0.47	1.61	3.73	64	2.79	0.64	1.61	4.70	126
AA	Ornithine	hmdb:HMDB0000214	99.77	24.18	49.32	160.57	62	76.94	24.46	41.80	152.85	64	88.69	26.57	41.80	160.57	126
AA	Saccharopine	hmdb:HMDB0000279	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06	59	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	49	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	108
AA	Sarcosine	hmdb:HMDB0000271	1.65	0.56	0.71	3.50	62	1.32	0.48	0.58	3.81	64	1.47	0.56	0.58	3.81	126
AA	Taurine	hmdb:HMDB0000251	58.35	13.28	34.28	101.75	62	56.96	12.27	31.00	87.95	64	57.62	12.77	31.00	101.75	126
ACRN	(3Z)-9-Hydroxyhexadecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0241475	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	39	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	35	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	74
ACRN	(9Z)-3-Hydroxydodecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240760	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.30	62	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.12	64	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.30	126
ACRN	(9Z)-3-Hydroxyoctadecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240761	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	(R)-3-hydroxybutyrylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0062735	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	126
ACRN	2-Octenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013324	0.13	0.09	0.05	0.61	62	0.10	0.07	0.03	0.40	64	0.12	0.08	0.03	0.61	126
ACRN	2-trans,4-cis-Decadienoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013325	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.08	62	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.08	126
ACRN	3, 5-Tetradecadienecarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013331	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.08	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	64	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.08	126
ACRN	3-Hydroxy-cis-5-octenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240766	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.07	126
ACRN	3-Hydroxy-cis-5-tetradecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013330	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.03	62	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	64	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.03	126
ACRN	3-Hydroxydecanoylcarnitine (C10:1-OH) [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	loinc:82478-9	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06	126
ACRN	3-hydroxy-dicarboxydecanoylcarnitine		NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	3-hydroxy-dicarboxyhexanoylcarnitine		NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	3-hydroxydodecanoyl carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0061638	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	126
ACRN	3-Hydroxyhexadecanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013336	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	3-Hydroxyisovalerylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0061189	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	62	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	126
ACRN	3-Hydroxyoctadecanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240769	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	3-Hydroxytetradecanoyl carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0061640	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	36	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	24	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	60
ACRN	3-Methylglutaryl carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000552	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.08	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.08	126

Reference values: metabolite concentrations [μM]			Male					Female					All				
Assay	Metabolite name	Database identifier (CURIE)	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N	Median	SD	Min	Max	N
ACRN	9,12-Hexadecadienoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013334	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	41	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	30	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	71
ACRN	9-Decenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013205	0.12	0.07	0.04	0.48	62	0.10	0.06	0.04	0.31	64	0.11	0.06	0.04	0.48	126
ACRN	9-Hexadecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013207	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	126
ACRN	C4-acylcarnitine	chebi:86490	0.18	0.09	0.06	0.47	62	0.16	0.09	0.09	0.68	64	0.17	0.09	0.06	0.68	126
ACRN	C5-acylcarnitine	chebi:86492	0.11	0.03	0.05	0.22	62	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.17	64	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.22	126
ACRN	cis-5-Tetradecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0002014	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.14	62	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.13	64	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.14	126
ACRN	Decanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000651	0.17	0.12	0.04	0.58	62	0.17	0.12	0.04	0.59	64	0.17	0.12	0.04	0.59	126
ACRN	Dodecanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0002250	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.20	62	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.21	64	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.21	126
ACRN	Glutaryl carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013130	0.07	0.02	0.03	0.14	62	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.14	64	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.14	126
ACRN	Hexanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000756	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.08	62	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.09	64	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.09	126
ACRN	L-Acetylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000201	5.15	1.72	3.01	10.74	62	5.36	1.69	2.88	10.25	64	5.31	1.69	2.88	10.74	126
ACRN	L-Carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000062	51.93	9.06	31.74	72.73	62	41.16	9.25	28.03	73.78	64	45.90	10.28	28.03	73.78	126
ACRN	Linoleyl carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0006469	0.07	0.02	0.03	0.17	62	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.09	64	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.17	126
ACRN	Malonylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0002095	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.12	62	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.10	64	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.12	126
ACRN	Methylmalonylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013133	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.06	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	64	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.06	126
ACRN	Octanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000791	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.34	62	0.10	0.06	0.03	0.27	64	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.34	126
ACRN	Oleoylecarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0005065	0.15	0.04	0.07	0.24	62	0.11	0.04	0.05	0.22	64	0.13	0.04	0.05	0.24	126
ACRN	Palmitoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000222	0.11	0.02	0.05	0.15	62	0.09	0.02	0.05	0.17	64	0.10	0.02	0.05	0.17	126
ACRN	Propionylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000824	0.41	0.15	0.25	1.06	62	0.31	0.14	0.12	1.07	64	0.37	0.15	0.12	1.07	126
ACRN	Sebacoyl-L-carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240726	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0
ACRN	Stearoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0000848	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.06	62	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.07	64	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.07	126
ACRN	Suberoyl-L-carnitine	hmdb:HMDB0240724	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	7	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	6	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	13
ACRN	Tetradecanoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0005066	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	62	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	64	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	126
ACRN	Tiglylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0002366	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	62	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	59	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	121
ACRN	trans-2-Dodecenoylcarnitine	hmdb:HMDB0013326	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.19	62	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.21	64	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.21	126
VLCFA	Behenic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000944	61.66	13.12	30.32	95.24	62	64.44	13.82	40.07	119.98	64	62.65	13.61	30.32	119.98	126
VLCFA	Hexacosanoic acid	hmdb:HMDB0002356	0.55	0.18	0.30	1.21	62	0.55	0.15	0.28	1.19	64	0.55	0.17	0.28	1.21	126
VLCFA	Phytanic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000801	1.80	1.01	0.85	5.29	62	2.35	1.47	1.08	8.76	64	1.94	1.30	0.85	8.76	126
VLCFA	Pristanic acid	hmdb:HMDB0000795	0.21	0.16	0.03	0.81	62	0.25	0.33	0.02	1.33	64	0.23	0.26	0.02	1.33	126
VLCFA	Tetracosanoic acid	hmdb:HMDB0002003	55.92	11.75	29.32	85.22	62	56.82	12.46	33.79	93.48	64	56.47	12.14	29.32	93.48	126

PCA, acylcarnitines

- 2022-02-02
- △ 2022-02-03
- + 2022-02-07
- × 2022-02-10

- FEMALE
- △ MALE

RDA, acylcarnitines ~ Measurement.date

RDA, acylcarnitines ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)

RDA, acylcarnitines ~ Number.of.freeze.thaw.cycles

RDA, acylcarnitines ~ Number.of.freeze.thaw.cycles + Condition(Measurement.date)

PCA, aminoacids

○ 2022-02-16
△ 2022-02-22

○ FEMALE
△ MALE

RDA, aminoacids ~ Measurement.date

RDA, aminoacids ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)

PCA, fattyacids

- 2022-02-18
- △ 2022-02-25
- + 2022-03-04
- × 2022-03-10
- ◇ 2022-03-11

- FEMALE
- △ MALE

RDA, fattyacids ~ Measurement.date

RDA, fattyacids ~ Measurement.date + Condition(Sex)

Appendix batch effect detection with ANOVA

Significant acylcarnitines

Metabolite	P-value
L-Carnitine	0.0016583
Propionylcarnitine	0.0024930
C4-acylcarnitine	0.0414878
C5-acylcarnitine	0.0000000
Palmitoylcarnitine	0.0141256
Stearoylcarnitine	0.0034880
Tiglylcarnitine	0.0416510
Linoleyl carnitine	0.0001293
Oleoylcarnitine	0.0449014
3-Hydroxyisovalerylcarnitine	0.0029762
3-Hydroxydecenoylcarnitine (C10:1-OH) [Moles/volume] in Serum or Plasma	0.0048602
(9Z)-3-Hydroxydodecenoylcarnitine	0.0074682
3-hydroxydodecanoyl carnitine	0.0000059
Methylmalonylcarnitine	0.0000467
Glutarylcarnitine	0.0006360
3-Methylglutarylcarnitine	0.0100362

Significant amino acids

Metabolite	P-value
3-Methylhistidine	0.0000025
L-Alanine	0.0007407
Aminoadipic acid	0.0000019
L-Alloisoleucine	0.0000816
Argininosuccinic acid	0.0000016
L-Aspartic acid	0.0000000
beta-Alanine	0.0000301
Citrulline	0.0022359
Ethanolamine	0.0000000
L-Phenylalanine	0.0000005
O-Phosphoethanolamine	0.0112530
L-Glutamic acid	0.0000000
L-Histidine	0.0014194
5-Hydroxylysine	0.0008022
4-Hydroxyproline	0.0000720
L-Isoleucine	0.0000002
L-Leucine	0.0000004
L-Lysine	0.0002433
L-Methionine	0.0014153
Ornithine	0.0000132
L-Proline	0.0000247
Saccharopine	0.0058158
L-Tryptophan	0.0000098
L-Tyrosine	0.0002102
L-Valine	0.0000003